

GAMIFIED VIDEO-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL IN TEACHING CLIMATE CHANGE AWARENESS FOR GRADE 12 STUDENTS

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Gamified Video-Based Instructional Material in Teaching Climate Change Awareness for Grade 12 Students

John Paul P. Cator*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to develop and evaluate the acceptability of gamified video-based instructional material for teaching climate change awareness among grade 12 students. It also attempted to find out the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students before and after utilizing the instructional material. This employed a quasi-experimental method of research. The respondents were sixty (60) grade twelve students under TVL-HE from two sections in a Public School in the Province of Quezon who were purposively chosen in this study for September to March of the school year 2023-2024. Weighted mean and paired sample t-test were used as the statistical treatment. Initially, a survey questionnaire was used to determine the level of climate change awareness of the students and assess their mean performance in Earth and Life Science through a pretest. From the results, gamified video-based instructional material was developed and validated. Also, an acceptability questionnaire was administered to 10 teachers and 10 student respondents. The respondents agreed that the instructional material is highly acceptable and valid for teaching climate change awareness and can help improve learners' performance. Findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the students in both the control and experimental groups. However, the use of gamified video-based instructional material better increased the performance of the students as compared to the traditional method. Therefore, it is recommended that the developed gamified video-based instructional material be used as an effective alternative instructional material for teaching climate change awareness.

Keywords: *acceptability, climate change awareness, gamified video-based instructional material, quasi-experimental method, TVL-HE students*

Introduction

One of the harmful environmental problems that threatens all people is climate change, which is the outcome of global warming. Different nations are employing a variety of strategies to reduce this risk and even work together to minimize or end this problem on Mother Earth. Various teachers think that including environmental awareness in the course can address this issue; in fact, they think that one way to address this issue is through proper education (Miparanum & Miparanum, 2023).

Currently, the belief that this generation will experience the worst effects of climate change has directed to an intensification in the number of young people who are presently concerned about these consequences. The success of the school strikes demanding political and economic changes in response to climate change demonstrates their growing concern for the environment (Ortega & Klauth, 2017).

Moreover, education helps students make informed choices and can motivate them to change their attitudes and habits. With this, students can learn how to adapt to climate change and the effects and impacts of global warming in the classroom and their environment. All individuals are empowered by education, but young people are especially inspired to create change and take action (Climate Change Education, n.d.). As a result, it's essential to promote scientific and critical thinking while also improving students' ability to investigate and fully understand concepts and phenomena. However, there has been a noticeable growth in the utilization of gamified video-based instructional materials in scientific classrooms that increase motivation, engagement, and enjoyment while supporting activities that are relevant to science education (Papadakis, Kalogiannakis, & Zaranis, 2018).

Notably, more and more gamified video-based instructional materials have emerged in recent years. There are a ton of games made expressly for education. Numerous gamified video-based instructional materials for enjoyment have also been employed in instruction or training (Baer, 2021). Clearly, the use of well-made instructional games can help students become more interested in a subject. Knowing which games are appropriate is helpful because they may also be time-consuming distractions (Nacional, 2023).

Moreover, raising environmental awareness and, thereby, understanding of the impacts of climate change will enable both behavioral change and societal support for the actions needed to reduce environmental problems. Therefore, the main purpose of this study is to determine students' level of climate change awareness and to make them attentive of what's going on around us through the utilization of gamified video-based instructional material in teaching that will help them fully understand climate change and the actions needed to take towards our environment.

Research Objectives

This research aimed to test the acceptability of gamified video-based instructional material in teaching climate change awareness to grade 12 students. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the level of climate change awareness of the students in terms of:

- 1.1. environmental problems;
- 1.2. attitudes and concerns towards environmental protection; and
- 1.3. participation and engagement level in environmental conservation.
2. Assess the mean performance of TVL-HE students in Earth and Life Science in terms of pretest.
3. Develop a gamified video-based instructional material in raising the level of awareness in climate change of students.
4. Test the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students before and after utilizing the gamified video-based instructional material.
5. Evaluate the acceptability of the gamified video-based instructional material based from the perceptions of teachers and students' respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. accuracy of the instructional material;
 - 2.2. clarity of the instructional material;
 - 2.3. appeal to target users; and
 - 2.4. originality in presentation.

Literature Review

Climate Change Awareness

Climate change awareness can be defined as the knowledge and understanding of environmental concepts and facts, as well as the consequences of various environmental problems such as pollution, overpopulation, deforestation, droughts, energy crises, and so forth. Social organizations and people can benefit from environmental awareness by becoming more aware of and comprehending environmental issues. Perhaps by acknowledging, looking into, and accepting the demands and issues that arise in life, one's environmental consciousness increases. Encouraging and valuing the environment to enhance one's social and personal life is another important aspect of environmental awareness. Furthermore, environmental consciousness can enhance a person's ability to see beauty in nature and enhance their aesthetic sense (Panth, Verma, & Gupta, 2015). Studies on environmental education have focused on students' environmental awareness and attitude because environmental education is thought to be a crucial means of educating students about environmental issues and concerns. Therefore, environmental education can be used to understand environmental awareness.

Green campus initiatives are being implemented by schools due to growing public awareness of environmental deterioration and concern for its restoration. According to Alata and Ignacio (2019), a green campus is a place where teaching and environmentally conscious practice coexist and where environmentally conscious principles are demonstrated through model behavior. The green campus institution serves as a model environmental community with interconnected academic programs, business operations, operational activities, and human resources that offer practical and educational benefits to the institution, the surrounding area, and the global community.

Educating our students about environmental awareness could be very beneficial in helping them to distinguish between different types of information on environmental sustainability and conservation. According to Raman (2016), the inclusion and integration of environmental education in the curriculum of all educational levels has a significant impact and major influence on students' knowledge, abilities, and attitudes about environmental conservation and protection. Furthermore, the majority of western universities currently prioritize the serious goals of studying environmental education.

Moreover, based on the data from the Department of Education's (DepEd) Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS) for the academic year (AY) 2009 - 2010 to AY 2017 - 2018, nearly 43,810 out of 47,000 public schools in the Philippines experienced and at risks of natural disasters at least once every eight (8) years. Of these, 39,738 schools were greatly affected by typhoons, while 25,191 were impacted by floodwaters, and 5,824 experienced coastal area problems and concerns. Droughts and sea level rise's effects on the education sector have not been taken into consideration. These statistics offer resounding proof that young people continue to be one of the most susceptible demographics to the effects of climate change and that they are feeling its effects across the board.

Furthermore, the physical, mental, social, and emotional development of young people is in danger due to unfavorable climatic conditions and extreme weather events like typhoons and droughts. According to a UNICEF report, the numerous threats to children's survival, security, and access to government services in the Philippines, including education, nutrition, health, water and sanitation, are made worse by climate change (Ortega & Klauth, 2017).

In the study of Christopher et al. (2019), it was stated that students should continue to have an extreme high level of environmental awareness and concerns, but education should raise it even further. This could be accomplished by providing students with the chance to form a personal bond with the environment, integrating media literacy into all subjects taught in the classroom, or using the school as a test or demonstration site for environmental awareness initiatives.

Similarly, Njoku (n.d.) stated that the effects of climate change are widespread, and it is important to inform students about these risks at an early age to foster a healthy attitude toward the environment and lower the risks related to it, leading to a sustainable way of life. The study revealed that students are keen to learn more about topics connected to sustainable development and climate change, even when they already possess some knowledge of these topics.

In addition, Abbas and Singh (2014) asserted that encouraging learners to participate in environmental conservation and protection initiatives may involve more than just their awareness of and access to information about their immediate environment. So also, the study emphasized that high level of environmental awareness has direct relation with acquiring good attitudes and higher sense of responsibility and concerns towards environment.

Additionally, the research study conducted by Uy, Manzanero, and Rebong (2019) showed that the households in Real, Quezon, successfully employed both the expected form of adaptation and long-term planning for climate change adaptation in their strategies to reduce the effects of climate change in their community. Most respondents are always concerned about their family, neighborhood, and safety during a strong storm. They have a positive outlook on climate change, which they attribute to their grasp of how to adapt to it. The study found that households abide by the regulations and help the local government improve its adaptation strategies since it strives to lessen the most severe effects of climate change. Although households are fully mindful of measures for adapting to climate change through television, radio, and seminars, human nature nonetheless causes them to fear and worry about the calamities that climate change would bring about.

Meanwhile, in the study of Abbas and Singh (2014), the results showed that even students are highly aware of environmental problems, this awareness does not always transfer into active involvement in conservation and advancement. This implies that there might be other things besides having information about the surroundings that could increase students' degree of participation. This requires more investigation into whether other elements are crucial for promoting community involvement in general and student participation in particular. All of this will guarantee the long-term survival of the ecosystem and the successful accomplishment of environmental education goals.

Nevertheless, Orr (1992) as cited in Alata and Ignacio (2019, p.80) argued that a person who is ecologically literate comprehends the mechanism of the environmental devastation, including the reasons for people's damaging behavior. In order to look at students' behavior, attitudes, sensitivity, and behavioral intention, it is required to determine their ecological literacy levels, and in order to increase awareness among students, it is vital to promote truthful and accurate knowledge to guarantee a positive attitude toward the environment.

Climate Change Education in the Philippines

The Climate Change Act of 2009 (Republic Act No. 9729) states that the Philippines has long recognized the need for climate change education. Meanwhile, the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, also known as the K-12 Curriculum Act, improved the way that important climate change concepts are integrated into the curriculum in subjects like Science, Health, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, and Araling Panlipunan, for students in kindergarten through junior high school.

In senior high school, particularly in the Science, Technology, Engineering, And Mathematics (STEM) strand, a Disaster Readiness and Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) special subject is available. Furthermore, Earth Science and Earth and Life Science both include competencies related to climate change. Co-curricular activities such as the formation of the Youth for Environment in Schools Organization (YES-O) (D.O. 93, s. 2011) and the integration of Solid Waste Management, Gulayan Sa Paaralan, and Tree Planting under the National Greening Program (NGP) (D.O. 5, s. 2014) were implemented to supplement the curriculum modifications (Ortega & Klauth, 2017).

Additionally, the Department of Education (DepEd) has issued various memorandums (OUA Memos 00-0920-0168, 12-019-0341, and 12-1119-0504) which spread awareness and instruct heads to provide absences to students who participated in the climate strike, provided that they can show documentation of agreement from their parents or guardians. These memos support students' participation in climate strikes.

Effectiveness of Gamified Learning Environments

Gamification has been used in the field of education as well as other sectors since it was first introduced ten years ago. As elaborated in the study of Kalogiannakis, Papadakis, and Zourmpakis (2021), gamification is the practice of inspiring students through non-gaming applications by utilizing aesthetics, game mechanics, game design elements, and game thinking. On the other hand, even though there isn't a particular word for gamification, most of them share specific characteristics.

However, gamification has recently shifted its attention to using digital platforms and applications to engage students virtually through the use of computers, tablets, and smartphones. While the playful objectives correspond to the gamification application's game design elements, their psychological requirements, motivational strength, and nature are all related to the gamification content, which determines the learning objectives.

According to Huang and Soman (2013), as cited in Kalogiannakis et al., (2021), playful goals and learning goals are interchangeable. Gamification's main goal is to influence factors such as motivation in order to affect a behavior related to learning, like interaction with the instructional material, and to attain a learning objective. Consequently, the purpose of gamification is to influence psychological variables that intercede the learning objectives (Kam et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, the way that instructional content is delivered can have an equal impact on learning outcomes as participation and effort

levels since it can lead to a decline in performance or the acquisition of knowledge and skills. A gamified learning environment needs to be carefully designed, especially in terms of the game elements it uses, and it also needs to have clear and simple instructions. If not, students could lose focus on their learning goals (Ijaz, Bogdanovych, & Trescak, 2017).

Impact of Gamification in Student Engagement and Motivation

In order to increase student engagement and maintain motivation, games can offer objectives, communication, feedback, problem solving, competition, narrative, and enjoyable learning situations. This instructional resource scrutinizes the differences between gamification and game-based learning, the educational advantages of both strategies, and the kinds of game elements that work well in both virtual and in-person learning contexts (University of Waterloo, n.d.).

According to Nacional (2023) gamification is an innovative technique that can improve learning results, motivation, and student involvement in the classroom. But there are still gaps in instructors' knowledge, and there are questions about whether or not students would embrace the gamification approach. Understanding gamification's definition, guiding principles, possible advantages, and drawbacks is essential for implementing it successfully in the classroom.

Educators can make informed choices about the integration of gamification in the educational system by understanding the effects it has on learner's engagement and motivation. Examining how gamified video-based instructional material functions in environmental education might help in raising students' knowledge of environmental problems and motivating them to adopt sustainable practices.

The gamified video-based instructional material is intended to resemble real-world challenges and situations, and the goal is to make the student feel more satisfied, motivated, and satisfied when they utilize the game application by making use of a certain number of game elements (Richter, Raban, & Rafaeli, 2015). However, according to Landers (2014) in Kalogiannakis et al., (2021) the main distinction between gamification and serious gaming in the classroom is the learning process and outcomes.

Moreover, learning is meaningfully affected by serious games since the educational content included in the software promotes learning. Every gamification application has two sets of objectives: learning objectives linked to the content and entertainment objectives related to the good user experiences they provide, like contentment and happiness (Sailer et al., 2017).

Additionally, a study conducted by Huang, Liaw, and Lai (2016) revealed that gamification has the potential in improving the student satisfaction and learning results. One set of students participated in gamified learning activities as part of the study's experimental design, while the other group attended a conventional lecture. The findings demonstrated that, in comparison to the group that studied through a traditional lecture, greater learning results and satisfaction were observed in the group engaging with gamified video-based learning activities.

Gamification Strategies in Climate Change Education

The idea and application of gamification in educational settings are relatively new; however, the usage of games in a learning environment is not new (Orhan Gökşün & Gürsoy, 2019). Numerous gamification studies have discovered that a variety of contextual elements, such as the population being targeted and the nature of the gamified activity, have an impact on the use of gamified video-based instructional material in education. However, gamification focuses more on higher education than on basic or secondary education, despite the fact that game-based learning literature has been more focused on these areas in primary and secondary education.

Furthermore, it is important to support active, scientific thinking in students while improving their investigation and comprehension of concepts and events. As a result, there has been a perceptible growth and development in the integration of gamification in science education to enhance motivation, satisfaction, and engagement with appropriate activities that support science education (Papadakis, Kalogiannakis, & Zaranis, 2018).

Moreover, gamification is frequently used together with socially active and productive learning environments (Chan et al., 2017). Gamified learning environments have been found to enhance students' responsiveness and willingness to engage in similar learning in the future. Finding innovative teaching techniques that will get learners interested in scientific education has taken a lot of effort. Based on the concepts of gamified video-based and active learning, gamification gives students specific learning goals and boosts their internal and external desire to finish their schoolwork. However, a variety of other teaching strategies, including project-based learning, experiential learning, and inquiry-based learning, can also be made easier by it.

The two main objectives of science education are to develop scientifically literate professionals and to attain scientific literacy. One of the most recognized and vital means of achieving these objectives is through scientific inquiry. Since science is an inquiry-based discipline, inquiry-based learning has become prominent as a means of helping students understand science. Rather than relying just on lectures, students can now behave as scientists and actively create, engage in, and complete inquiry activities (Tsai, 2017).

Moreover, a few studies showed improvements in students' acquisition of science knowledge as well as an improvement in their higher-order and cognitive thinking skills. Inquiry-based learning issues like time consumption, a lack of teacher support, or a lack of understanding about how to incorporate inquiry activities in conventional science classrooms are being addressed by researchers, who are also making use of recently created technological tools and innovations, like gamification, to enhance scientific inquiry activities (Riga et al., 2016).

Notably, gamification has also been shown to support researchers in the field of science education, which has experienced a decline in academic performance, student enrollment, and positive attitudes about science education globally. Researchers studying gamification in education have been confused by a range of contradicting findings about student achievement levels, despite some evidence that it can increase student engagement and enjoyment (Marín et al., 2018).

Challenges and Opportunities in Implementing Gamified Video-Based Instructional Materials

Gamification is an innovative approach of teaching that seeks to improve learning results, motivation, and student involvement. Gamification, however, can also present some problems that should be resolved.

A gamification program would need to be designed with progress indicators, challenges, success levels, feedback, and a competitive element (Huang & Hew, 2018). However, according to Matallaoui et al. (2016) it is important to establish clear, closely related objectives, create a balance between challenges and skill development, and emphasize the relationship between awareness and action. They are crucial for creating a gamified environment since some of them include prerequisites for flow and are closely related to engagement and motivation. A gamification application's design would need to have clear, attainable objectives, instant feedback, a progress indicator, and challenges that are respectively challenging given the users' overall skill level and perceived value of achieving them (Huang & Hew, 2018).

Furthermore, identifying, selecting, and using game design components to influence students' motivation and engagement is an essential component of gamification design. Nevertheless, gamification applications frequently diverge from a formal process design (Mora et al., 2017). They adhere to protocols and apply components randomly, like utilizing a leaderboard system, without taking into account extraneous considerations like the demographics and psychological needs of the students. These ad hoc methods pose a serious issue since they make it difficult to use certain features and procedures in other case studies. As a result, various researchers have emphasized how vital it is to classify and identify the benefits and drawbacks, effects, and overall impact of gaming features when they are used in an educational setting, then choose the most beneficial ones in accordance with formal protocols and particular objectives (Van Roy & Zaman, 2018).

Moreover, students becoming more motivated and engaged is one of the main advantages of gamification. Gamification has the potential to improve learners' desire to meet learning objectives by giving them a sense of progress and instant feedback (Huang et al., 2020). Additionally, gamification has the potential to enhance student collaboration and social interaction, resulting in a more dynamic and captivating learning environment.

Similarly, gamification works best when it is implemented carefully (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017). Duration and game components are important factors in the difficulties and successes of integrating gamification to achieve learning outcomes. This suggests that in creating a gamified lesson plan or class, educators should consider any potential challenges and negative effects that could arise throughout the implementation process.

In addition, to produce a meaningful outcome, the length will be at least six weeks to a semester. This could suggest that gamification is a continuous learning process that requires momentum maintenance rather than a one-time event. This is consistent with the behavioristic perspective, which maintains that experiences that humans have are shaped by occurrences in their surroundings (Anindyarini et al., 2018). To accomplish the course outcomes in the context of the students, teachers must carefully plan and implement gamified lessons.

In the study of Sabornido, Garma, Niepes and Cabria (2022) it has been determined that the primary challenges and difficulties encountered throughout the gamification process stem from the fact that certain students are not completely engaged, which could have a negative impact on the learner's overall performance and task completion. Negative effects on students' attitudes could result from poorly structured lessons. It also mentioned the six-week to semester implementation period and the game elements—points, level, and cooperation—that are utilized in higher education. Therefore, challenges and disadvantages will always arise, even with carefully thought-out design and implementation.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design applied in this study is the quasi-experimental design with self-made survey questionnaire, pretest, posttest, adopted acceptability test and observation as the main tool. This study most appropriately employed the quasi-experimental research design which typically apply elements of experimental design in a real-world setting. This allows for some level of control over the intervention, making it suitable for educational research. Using this approach helped to produce a clearer image from the quantitative data, which improved comprehension and the explanation of the relevant study. The researcher used this method in order to test the effectiveness of gamified video-based instructional material in teaching climate change awareness to students. The data from the instruments was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

The quasi-experimental method was used in this study, which as pointed out by Thomas (2020), aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable. By implementing an intervention and comparing results between groups,

quasi-experimental methods enable researchers to explore causal relationships.

Respondents

The respondents are sixty (60) selected Grade 12 students from two sections (Dignity and Nobility) under Technical-Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) - Home Economics Strand in a Public School in the Province of Quezon during the Academic Year 2023-2024. The participants were chosen purposively since they took the Earth and Life Science subject during their first semester, which has lessons related to climate change mitigation, which the study was primarily focused on. Respondents were grouped into Control (Grade 12-Dignity) and Experimental (Grade 12-Nobility) groups using the pretest-posttest non-equivalent group design method. With this method, respondents are divided into groups according to pre-existing traits such as gender, age, and academic standing. These groups are similar in composition, but not exactly the same.

In the acceptability test of the gamified video-based instructional material in teaching climate change awareness to students, ten (10) science experts and ten (10) students were chosen as respondents.

Instrument

The researcher used self-made survey questionnaire, pretest, posttest, adapted acceptability test and observation as his instruments. The instruments aimed to discover the level of awareness of the students in climate change and also attempted to test the acceptability level of the gamified video-based instructional material based on teachers and students' personal views on the use of this innovative instructional material in their teaching and learning. In this part, teachers and students were encouraged to give their views on their learning experience and to make recommendations for improving the gamified video-based instructional material in teaching climate change awareness.

To test the validity of the instruments, the researcher asked the assistance of experts in this nature of the study. The instruments were subjected to content and expert validation to determine the validity and suitability of every question for all the participants.

Procedure

In order to respond to the research questions that contributed to the development of the gamified video-based instructional material, the researcher employed the procedures systematically in gathering data.

First, the researcher sought permission from his adviser to allow him to conduct the study in a Public School in the Province of Quezon by letter of transmittal. After being granted permission, the researcher proceeded to the school's district supervisor and head of the school where the study was conducted. The letter of request that was signed and approved by the adviser of the researcher and was given to the head of the school for their permission to conduct the research study and used their students as respondents.

The quantitative data of this study was collected at the start of the grading period of the academic year through the administration of a survey questionnaire. Respondents were given 30 minutes to complete the questionnaire. The questionnaire is personally administered by the researcher in order to determine the level of climate change awareness of the students. All gathered data was tallied, analyzed, interpreted and statistically treated.

Then, the researcher created and developed the gamified video-based instructional material based on the results of the survey. This learning material was implemented with the experimental group of students to determine its effect on their level of awareness about climate change.

For the last part, to test the acceptability of the study, the teachers and students' learning experiences using the gamified video-based instructional material was conducted using Likert-scale questionnaire. At last, the results of the test were tallied, analyzed, interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

Observing ethical standards in research is essential. At the core, this helped shape the true aims of the study, such as knowledge, truth, and avoidance of error and promoted values essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. To ensure ethical research, this study followed and respected the principles of research ethics. These principles respect a person's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, informed consent, confidentiality and data protection, integrity, and conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, interpretation, analysis of data and findings of the study gathered from the respondents.

In presenting data, the researchers used tables that were carefully analyzed and interpreted, duly supported and justified by the review of related literature and studies.

Table 1.1 shows the weighted mean distribution of the level of climate change awareness of the students in terms of environmental problems. The participants agreed that they are aware of the different environmental problems in their community. The statement "I observe a lower level of coastline due to quarrying, which results in increasing sea levels in our community that affect the residential

areas near the seashore during heavy rains” ranked first with a weighted mean of 3.52 and a description of Strongly Agree/Highly Aware. Meanwhile, the statements “Garbage waste disposal and segregation problems are major issues in our environment” and “I have noticed more hot days and extreme hot temperatures as a significant change in our community” were both ranked second with a weighted mean of 3.37 and a description of Agree/Aware. On the other hand, the statement “Air and water pollution are a significant problem in our environment” ranked last with a weighted mean of 2.70 and a description of Agree/Aware.

Table 1.1. *Students’ Level of Climate Change Awareness about Environmental Problems*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. I am aware of the environmental problems in my community and their connection to climate change.	3.17	A	A
2. I feel well-informed about the causes and consequences of climate change.	3.12	A	A
3. I believe that climate change is primarily caused by human activities.	3.28	A	A
4. I observe a lower level of coastline due to quarrying, which results in increasing sea levels in our community that affect the residential areas near the seashore during heavy rains.	3.52	SA	HA
5. Deforestation is a major issue in our area.	2.73	A	A
6. Garbage waste disposal and segregation problems are major issues in our environment.	3.37	A	A
7. Overpopulation contributes to environmental problems.	3.10	A	A
8. Climate change has had an impact on my health.	3.33	A	A
9. Climate change has affected my level of stress.	2.75	A	A
10. I have noticed more hot days and extreme hot temperatures as a significant change in our community.	3.37	A	A
11. I observe the shortage of water sources in our community.	2.80	A	A
12. Air and water pollution are a significant problem in our environment.	2.70	A	A
13. Infectious diseases, for example, dengue fever, can possibly increase due to climate change events.	3.08	A	A
14. Climate extremes such as floods, landslides, and forest fires have caused deaths.	2.97	A	A
15. Shortage of fish supplies due to the extreme temperature affects major livelihoods in our community.	2.98	A	A
Average Weighted Mean	3.08	A	A

The result in the table implies that students are aware of the different environmental problems within their community and observed the significant changes that they have experienced in their environment. The high ranking of the statement regarding the observed lower coastline due to quarrying, which affects residential areas during heavy rains, suggests a strong awareness among students regarding the direct impact of environmental changes on their community. This indicates a potential opportunity for community-based interventions that address localized environmental challenges, such as quarrying activities impacting coastal areas. Additionally, the acknowledgment of garbage waste disposal and segregation problems, as well as the increase in hot days and extreme temperatures, highlights the recognition of broader environmental issues affecting the community. These findings underscore the importance of fostering community engagement and action to address systemic environmental challenges, such as waste management and climate change adaptation.

However, the lower ranking of the statement regarding air and water pollution indicates a potential knowledge gap or underestimation of the severity of these environmental issues within the community. This suggests a need for targeted educational efforts to raise awareness about the health and environmental impacts of air and water pollution and to advocate for policies and practices that mitigate these concerns.

Overall, the implications suggest the importance of tailoring environmental education and advocacy efforts to address specific local environmental issues while also providing broader context and understanding of global environmental challenges. By empowering students with knowledge and resources to address environmental issues in their community, educational institutions and policymakers can facilitate meaningful action towards building a more sustainable and resilient future.

The result conforms with the study of Christopher et al. (2019) that students should continue to have an extreme high level of environmental awareness and concerns, but education should raise it even further. This could be accomplished by providing students with the chance to form a personal bond with the environment, integrating media literacy into all subjects taught in the classroom, or using the school as a test or demonstration site for environmental awareness initiatives.

It can be gleaned from Table 1.2 that students agreed that they are aware of their attitudes and behaviors towards the environment that could have a positive and negative impact, as reflected in the average weighted mean of 3.09 and a descriptive rating of Agree/Aware. The statements “I turn off lights and appliances when not in use to conserve energy consumption” and “I try to reduce, reuse, and recycle items to minimize waste” ranked first and second with a weighted mean of 3.57 and 3.28 with a descriptive rating of Strongly Agree/Highly Aware and Agree/Aware, respectively. On the other hand, the statements “I actively seek information about climate change and environmental issues” and “I conserve water by reducing usage at home, which I believe is a good action for the environment” ranked lowest with a weighted mean of 2.80 and 2.77, respectively, with a descriptive rating of both Agree/Aware.

Given that statements related to energy conservation and waste reduction received higher ratings, it suggests that students already possess a certain level of awareness and engagement in these areas. Therefore, educational efforts should build upon this existing foundation by reinforcing and expanding knowledge and practices related to energy conservation and waste reduction. Thus, there is a

need for targeted educational initiatives to raise awareness about the importance of seeking information on climate change and environmental issues and promoting water conservation practices.

Table 1.2. *Students Level of Awareness about their Attitudes and Concerns towards Environmental Protection*

<i>Statements</i>		<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I actively seek information about climate change and environmental issues.	2.80	A	A
2.	I am concerned about the impact of climate change on the environment.	3.23	A	A
3.	I am willing to make lifestyle changes to reduce my environmental impact, even if it means some personal inconvenience.	3.12	A	A
4.	I reduce my energy consumption in response to what I have heard about global climate change.	2.97	A	A
5.	I believe that individual actions can make a positive impact on the environment.	3.10	A	A
6.	I encourage others to take action to combat climate change.	3.10	A	A
7.	I feel a sense of responsibility to protect the natural world for future generations.	3.20	A	A
8.	Concern for future generations and personal health and well-being motivates me to engage in environmental protection efforts.	3.27	A	A
9.	I used to walk or ride a bicycle instead of using a motorcycle and driving a gas-guzzling vehicle to reduce the high level of emissions of greenhouse gases that are harmful to the environment.	3.03	A	A
10.	I try to reduce, reuse, and recycle items to minimize waste.	3.28	A	A
11.	I turn off lights and appliances when not in use to conserve energy consumption.	3.57	SA	HA
12.	Supporting and purchasing products with environmentally-friendly labels and certifications is a responsible choice.	3.02	A	A
13.	I prevent littering and regularly practice properly disposing of trash to lessen plastic waste.	3.08	A	A
14.	I conserve water by reducing usage at home which I believe is a good action for the environment.	2.77	A	A
15.	I minimize using single-use plastic products like bags and bottles contributes to environmental pollution.	2.88	A	A
Average Weighted Mean		3.09	A	A

This is parallel to the study of Njoku (n.d.) who stated that the effects of climate change are widespread, and it is important to inform students about these risks at an early age to foster a healthy attitude toward the environment and lower the risks related to it, leading to a sustainable way of life. The study revealed that students are keen to learn more about topics connected to sustainable development and climate change, even when they already possess some knowledge of these topics.

Table 1.3. *Students Participation and Engagement Level towards Environmental Conservation*

<i>Statements</i>		<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I support or participate in environmental conservation or clean-up initiatives.	2.97	A	A
2.	I have taken personal actions to reduce my carbon footprint (e.g., using public transportation, reducing plastic waste, conserving energy).	2.80	A	A
3.	I have influenced my friends or family to take actions to mitigate climate change.	2.88	A	A
4.	I have volunteered for climate change-related programs, organizations or initiatives in my barangay.	2.70	A	A
5.	I have actively engaged in discussions or projects related to climate change within my local community.	2.83	A	A
6.	I frequently engage in discussions or activities related to environmental protection and climate change with my friends or family.	2.85	A	A
7.	I am willing to increase my efforts in climate change mitigation in the future.	3.13	A	A
8.	I am aware of the climate change and environmental protection programs and projects in my school or community.	3.08	A	A
9.	I actively participate in environmental clubs and organizations in school like YES-O and Science Club that motivates students' engagement towards environmental protection.	2.62	A	A
10.	I participate in tree-planting activities at school to mitigate climate change.	3.23	A	A
11.	I do garden at school and at home as a simple way to protect our environment.	3.28	A	A
12.	I've actively participated in climate change and environmental protection activities despite a busy schedule.	2.87	A	A
13.	I have successfully managed to actively participate in climate change and environmental protection activities despite lack of information about available programs/projects at school and at our own community.	2.85	A	A
14.	Despite resource limitations (e.g. transportation, materials), I've creatively contributed to environmental causes, showcasing resilience.	2.95	A	A
15.	Despite the initial lack of support from teachers or community leaders, I am determined to actively engage and participate in climate change and environmental protection activities, finding innovative ways to contribute and make a positive impact.	3.40	A	A
Average Weighted Mean		2.96	A	A

Table 1.3 reveals the weighted mean distribution of students' participation and engagement level towards environmental conservation. The statements "Despite the initial lack of support from teachers or community leaders, I am determined to actively engage and participate in climate change and environmental protection activities, finding innovative ways to contribute and make a positive impact"

and “I do garden at school and at home as a simple way to protect our environment” ranked first and second with a weighted mean of 3.40 and 3.28, respectively, respectively, with a descriptive rating of both Agree/Aware. On the other side, the statements “I have volunteered for climate change-related programs, organizations or initiatives in my barangay” and “I actively participate in environmental clubs and organizations in school like YES-O and Science Club that motivates students’ engagement towards environmental protection” ranked lowest with a weighted mean of 2.70 and 2.62, respectively, respectively, with a descriptive rating of both Agree/Aware. Overall, the students’ participation and engagement level towards environmental conservation got an average weighted mean of 2.96 and a description of Agree/Aware.

As an implication based on the results mentioned above, the high ranking of statements indicating individual determination to participate in climate change and environmental protection activities, despite initial lack of support from teachers or community leaders, suggests a strong intrinsic motivation among students to make a positive impact. This underscores the resilience and commitment of students towards environmental conservation, indicating a potential opportunity for educational institutions and community leaders to leverage and support students’ initiative in driving environmental change. Additionally, the recognition of gardening as a simple way to protect the environment highlights the importance of promoting hands-on and practical approaches to environmental conservation within educational settings. Encouraging activities such as gardening not only fosters a direct connection to nature but also instills a sense of responsibility and stewardship towards the environment from an early age.

Overall, the implications suggest the importance of creating an inclusive and supportive environment that empowers students to actively engage in environmental conservation efforts. By providing opportunities for hands-on involvement, fostering intrinsic motivation, and offering support and resources, educational institutions and community leaders can nurture a generation of environmentally conscious and active citizens capable of driving meaningful change towards a sustainable future.

The results conform with the study of Abbas and Singh (2014), the results showed that even students are highly aware of environmental problems, this awareness does not always transfer into active involvement in conservation and advancement. This implies that there might be other things besides having information about the surroundings that could increase students’ degree of participation. This requires more investigation into whether other elements are crucial for promoting community involvement in general and student participation in particular. All of this will guarantee the long-term survival of the ecosystem and the successful accomplishment of environmental education goals.

Table 2. Mean Performance of the TVL-HE Students in Earth and Life Science Before and After Utilizing the Developed Gamified Video-Based Instructional Material

Group		MPS	SD	Interpretation
Experimental Group	Pretest	54.83	3.65	Needs Improvement
	Posttest	79.17	3.35	Good Performance
Control Group	Pretest	45.67	4.38	Needs Improvement
	Posttest	65.00	4.06	Fair Performance

Table 2 presents the Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) and Standard Deviations (SD) for both the experimental and control groups before and after exposure to gamified video-based instructional material. The interpretation of the MPS for each group provides insights into the effectiveness of the instructional intervention in improving students’ performance in understanding climate change awareness.

The experimental group initially exhibited a need for improvement in their understanding of climate change awareness, as indicated by the pretest MPS (54.83) falling below the threshold for satisfactory performance. However, following exposure to the gamified video-based instructional material, there was a significant improvement in performance, with the posttest MPS (79.17) reaching the level of good performance. This suggests that the instructional intervention effectively enhanced students’ knowledge and comprehension of climate change concepts.

Similarly, the control group demonstrated a need for improvement in their initial performance regarding climate change awareness, with the pretest MPS (45.67) falling below satisfactory levels. While there was an improvement in performance after the intervention, as evidenced by the posttest MPS (65.00) reaching the level of fair performance, it was not as substantial as observed in the experimental group. This indicates that factors other than the gamified video-based instructional material may have influenced the improvement in performance among the control group.

As an implication, the gamified video-based instructional material had a significant positive impact on improving students’ understanding of climate change awareness in the experimental group. The results highlight the effectiveness of integrating technology and gamification into educational practices for enhancing learning outcomes. Educators can consider incorporating similar instructional approaches to promote engagement and comprehension of complex topics such as climate change among students.

According to Nacional (2023) gamification is an innovative technique that can improve learning results, motivation, and student involvement in the classroom. Moreover, gamification is frequently used together with socially active and productive learning environments (Chan et al., 2017). Gamified learning environments have been found to enhance students’ responsiveness and willingness to engage in similar learning in the future. Finding innovative teaching techniques that will get learners interested in scientific education has taken a lot of effort. Gamification, which is based on game-based and active learning principles, provides students with clear

learning objectives and increases their motivation to complete schoolwork both internally and externally. However, a variety of other teaching strategies, including project-based learning, experiential learning, and inquiry-based learning, can also be made easier by it.

Table 3. Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Students

Groupings	T	p	Interpretation
Control	-4.252	0.000	Significant
Experimental	-7.814	0.000	Significant

Table 3 reveals significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in both the control and experimental groups before and after the utilization of gamified video-based instructional material. For the control group, the computed t-value of -4.252 with a p-value of 0.000 indicates a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. Similarly, for the experimental group, the computed t-value of -7.814 with a p-value of 0.000 also indicates a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores at 0.05 level of significance. This means that both the control and experimental groups show significant improvements in their posttest scores compared to their pretest scores. These results provide strong evidence supporting the effectiveness of the developed gamified video-based instructional material applied to experimental group in teaching climate change awareness.

The results are parallel to the study of Huang, Liaw, and Lai (2016) who found out that gamification has the potential in improving the student satisfaction and learning results. One set of students participated in gamified learning activities as part of the study's experimental design, while the other group attended a conventional lecture. The findings demonstrated that, in comparison to the group that studied through a traditional lecture, greater learning results and satisfaction were observed in the group engaging with gamified video-based learning activities.

Table 4.1. Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Instructional Material in terms of Accuracy

	Accuracy Of The Instructional Material	Teacher		Student		Overall	
		WM	DR	WM	DR	WM	DR
1.	The topics are well arranged to provide clear sequence of understanding.	3.50	A	3.40	A	3.45	A
2.	The instructional material provides sufficient information about the chosen topics for easy understanding.	3.50	A	3.50	A	3.50	A
3.	Ideas and concepts are well explained in the instructional material.	3.60	HA	3.60	HA	3.60	HA
4.	The instructional material is appropriate to the age, maturity and experiences for the readers	3.60	HA	3.60	HA	3.60	HA
5.	The instructional material relates to the present learning and engagements of the students in science.	3.60	HA	3.80	HA	3.70	HA
Average Weighted Mean						3.57	HA

The developed gamified video-based instructional material is accepted through the four categories: accuracy of the material, clarity of the material, appeal to the target users, and originality of the instructional material.

Table 4.1 shows the weighted mean distribution in terms of accuracy of the instructional material. The five (5) items statements have the weighted mean of 3.45, 3.50, 3.60, 3.60 and 3.70, respectively with the average weighted mean of 3.57. The average weighted mean is rated as highly acceptable which means that the developed material is highly acceptable in terms of its accuracy. Based on the results, the topics are well arranged to provide the clear sequence of the understanding. It also provides sufficient information about the chosen topics for easy understanding. The result concludes that the material relates to the present learning and engagements of the student in science specifically in climate change topics.

Similarly, gamification's main goal is to influence factors such as motivation in order to affect a behavior related to learning, like interaction with the instructional material, and to attain a learning objective. Consequently, the purpose of gamification is to influence psychological variables that intercede the learning objectives (Kam et al., 2018).

Table 4.2. Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Instructional Material in terms of Clarity

	Clarity Of The Instructional Material	Teacher		Student		Overall	
		WM	DR	WM	DR	WM	DR
1.	The concept in the instructional material is clear and easy to understand.	3.60	HA	3.60	HA	3.60	HA
2.	The audio components (e.g., narration) in the instructional material contribute to a better understanding of the content.	3.10	A	3.20	A	3.15	A
3.	The text and written content in the materials are well-structured and easy to understand.	3.70	HA	3.70	HA	3.70	HA
4.	The animations and interactive elements help the users to navigate and use the instructional material easily.	3.70	HA	3.80	HA	3.75	HA
5.	The information in the instructional material is easy to understand.	3.50	A	3.40	A	3.45	A
Average Weighted Mean						3.53	HA

Table 4.2 shows the weighted mean distribution in terms of clarity of the instructional material. The five (5) items statements have the weighted mean of 3.60, 3.15, 3.70, 3.75 and 3.45, respectively with the average weighted mean of 3.53. The average weighted mean is rated as highly acceptable in terms of clarity of the material. According to the result, this connotes that the contents are organized and vivid. It presents attractive, well-structured, and easily understandable concepts and it contains some of the graphics to be grasped by the target users.

As a whole, the average weighted mean of 3.53 indicates that the gamified video-based instructional material is accepted to provide an opportunity for teachers and students to understand clearly the concepts, strategies and techniques presented and enhance the learning they have.

A gamified learning environment needs to be carefully designed, especially in terms of the game elements it uses, and it also needs to have clear and simple instructions. If not, students could lose focus on their learning goals (Ijaz, Bogdanovych, & Trescak, 2017). Moreover, a gamification application's design would need to have clear, attainable objectives, instant feedback, a progress indicator, and challenges that are respectively challenging given the users' overall skill level and perceived value of achieving them (Huang & Hew, 2018).

Table 4.3. *Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Instructional Material in terms of Appeal to Target Users*

<i>Appeal To Target Users Of The Instructional Material</i>		<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>
1.	The title used in the instructional material captures the interest of the target users.	3.60	HA	3.50	A	3.55	HA
2.	The instructional material presented in a pace attracts the target users' attention.	3.40	A	3.50	A	3.45	A
3.	The instructional material stimulates the users to have interest to engage the students in learning.	3.60	HA	3.50	A	3.55	HA
4.	The graphics and visuals in the instructional material are attractive to the users.	3.60	HA	3.60	HA	3.60	HA
5.	The text and written content in the materials are well-structured and easy to understand	3.60	HA	3.70	HA	3.65	HA
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>						3.56	HA

Table 4.3 shows the weighted mean distribution in terms of its appeal to the target users. The five (5) items statements have the weighted mean of 3.55, 3.45, 3.55, 3.60 and 3.65, respectively with the average weighted mean of 3.56. The average weighted mean is rated as highly acceptable which means that the developed material is highly acceptable in terms of its appeal to the target users. The researcher developed the instructional material to captures the interest of the target users. It attracts the attention of the learners through the help of simple but attractive graphics which stimulates the user to have interest in engaging climate change related topics.

Learning is meaningfully affected by serious games since the educational content included in the software promotes learning. Every gamification application has two sets of objectives: learning objectives linked to the content and entertainment objectives related to the good user experiences they provide, like contentment and happiness (Sailer et al., 2017).

Table 4.4. *Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Instructional Material in terms of Originality*

<i>Originality In Presentation Of The Instructional Material</i>		<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DR</i>
1.	The instructional material has design and appearance that are exceptional from other instructional materials.	3.50	A	3.10	A	3.30	A
2.	The instructional material serves as a new basic model in teaching and learning strategies.	3.50	A	3.70	HA	3.60	HA
3.	The instructional material uses graphics that are distinct and unusual.	3.50	A	3.50	A	3.50	A
4.	The instructional material is developed to accommodate alternative strategies and techniques for the users.	3.60	HA	3.30	A	3.45	A
5.	The developed instructional material serves as teaching guide to uplift student engagements in science.	3.70	HA	3.50	A	3.60	HA
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>						3.49	A

Table 4.4 shows the weighted mean distribution in terms of its originality. The five (5) items statements have the weighted mean of 3.30, 3.60, 3.50, 3.45 and 3.60, respectively with an average weighted mean of 3.49. The average weighted mean is rated acceptable that the developed gamified video-based instructional material is acceptable in terms of its originality. According to the results, this material will serve as a new basic model in teaching and learning strategies. It is also developed to accommodate alternative strategies and technique for the users and to serves as teaching guide to uplift students' engagements in science. Various researchers have emphasized how vital it is to classify and identify the benefits and drawbacks, effects, and overall impact of gaming features when they are used in an educational setting, then choose the most beneficial ones in accordance with formal protocols and particular objectives (Van Roy & Zaman, 2018).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived:

The students totally agreed that they are aware of the environmental problems, attitudes and concerns towards environmental protection, and participation and engagement level in environmental conservation. With this shared understanding and commitment, the students stand poised to make significant strides in addressing environmental problems and safeguarding the environment for generations to come.

Both the experimental and control group initially exhibited a need for improvement in their understanding of climate change awareness which indicates a shared baseline level of knowledge and comprehension among the students, highlighting the great need for educational interventions to enhance understanding in this area.

The developed gamified video-based instructional material in teaching climate change awareness among grade 12 students is ready for pilot teaching.

The use of gamified video-based instructional material in teaching climate change awareness better increased the performance of the students as compared to the traditional method.

The developed gamified video-based instructional material is highly acceptable and valid instructional material in teaching climate change awareness to students and can help improve learners' performance.

References

- Abbas, M. Y., & Singh, R. (2014). A Survey of environmental Awareness, Attitude and Participation amongst university students: a case study [PhD Dissertation, Lovely Professional University (LPU), Phagwara, Punjab State, India]. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336133232_A_Survey_of_Environmental_Awareness_Attitude_
- Anindyarini, A., Rokhman, F., Mulyani, M., & Andayani. (2018). Behavioristic Theory and Its Application in the Learning of Speech. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(9), 522. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i9.2714>
- Baer, S. (2021, May 12). The Rise Of Educational Games. *eLearning Industry*. <https://elearningindustry.com/rise-of-educational-games>
- Chan, K. Y. G., Tan, S. L., Hew, K. F. T., Koh, B. G., Lim, L. S., & Yong, J. C. (2017). Knowledge for games, games for knowledge: designing a digital roll-and-move board game for a law of torts class. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-016-0045-1>
- Christopher, H. P., Cherry, M. C. S., Teresa, C. S. M., & Arlyne, C. M. (2019). ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS OF SELECTED URBAN AND RURAL HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE PHILIPPINES. *I-manager S Journal on School Educational Technology*, 15(2), 15. <https://doi.org/10.26634/jsch.15.2.16664>
- Climate change education: How can environmental education help to combat climate change? (By Iberdrola Group). (n.d.). Iberdrola. <https://www.iberdrola.com/social-commitment/climate-change-education>
- Dichev, C., & Dicheva, D. (2017). Gamifying education: what is known, what is believed and what remains uncertain: a critical review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0042-5>
- Enhancing Learning through Game-Based Techniques | Centre for Teaching Excellence. (n.d.). University of Waterloo. <https://uwaterloo.ca/centre-for-teaching-excellence/enhancing-learning-through-game-based-techniques>
- Göksün, D. O., & Gürsoy, G. (2019). Comparing success and engagement in gamified learning experiences via Kahoot and Quizizz. *Computers & Education*, 135, 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.02.015>
- Huang, B., & Hew, K. F. (2018). Implementing a theory-driven gamification model in higher education flipped courses: Effects on out-of-class activity completion and quality of artifacts. *Computers & Education*, 125, 254–272.
- Huang, H., Liaw, S., & Lai, C. (2016). Exploring Learner Acceptance of the Use of Virtual Reality in Medical Education: A Case Study of Desktop and Projection-Based Display Systems. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1087902>
- Huang, R., Ritzhaupt, A. D., Sommer, M., Zhu, J., Stephen, A., Valle, N., Hampton, J., & Li, J. (2020). The impact of gamification in educational settings on student learning outcomes: a meta-analysis. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(4), 1875–1901. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09807-z>
- Ijaz, K., Bogdanovych, A., & Trescak, T. (2016). Virtual worlds vs books and videos in history education. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 25(7), 904–929. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2016.1225099>
- Kalogiannakis, M., Papadakis, S., & Zourmpakis, A. (2021). Gamification in Science Education. A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Education Sciences*, 11(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11010022>

- Kam, A. H. T., Umar, I. N., School of Engineering, Taylor's University, & Centre for Instructional Technology & Multimedia, Universiti Sains Malaysia, 11800, USM, Pulau Pinang, Malaysia. (2018). FOSTERING AUTHENTIC LEARNING MOTIVATIONS THROUGH GAMIFICATION: A SELF-DETERMINATION THEORY (SDT) APPROACH. In *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology: Vol. Special Issue on i-CITE 2018* (pp. 1–9). https://jestec.taylors.edu.my/i-Cite%202018/i-Cite_01.pdf
- Marín, B., Frez, J., Cruz-Lemus, J., & Genero, M. (2018). An Empirical Investigation on the Benefits of Gamification in Programming Courses. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education*, 19(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3231709>
- Matalallaoui, A., Hanner, N., & Zarnekow, R. (2016). Introduction to Gamification: Foundation and Underlying Theories. In *Progress in IS* (pp. 3–18). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45557-0_1
- Miparanum, C. M., & Miparanum, C. B. (2023). Climate Change Strategies' Model in Teaching Science 7. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8058282>
- Mora, A., Riera, D., González, C., & Arnedo-Moreno, J. (2017). Gamification: a systematic review of design frameworks. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 29(3), 516–548. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12528-017-9150-4>
- Nacional, R. (2023). Gamifying Education: Enhancing Student Engagement and Motivation [Department of Education, Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School District of Carmona, Division of Cavite Province, Philippines]. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372689745_Gamifying_Education_Enhancing_Student_Engagement_and_Motivation
- Njoku, C. (n.d.). Awareness of Climate Change and Sustainable Development Issues among Junior Secondary School (JSS) Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1207326>
- Ortega, J. B., & Klauth, C. (2017). Climate Landscape Analysis for Children in the Philippines [PDF file]. UNICEF Philippines.
- Panth, M. K., Verma, P., & Gupta, M. (2015). The Role of Attitude in Environmental Awareness of Under Graduate Students. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, 2(7), 55–62. <https://www.ijrhss.org/pdf/v2-i7/6.pdf>
- Papadakis, S., Kalogiannakis, M., & Zaranis, N. (2018). The effectiveness of computer and tablet assisted intervention in early childhood students' understanding of numbers. An empirical study conducted in Greece. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(5), 1849–1871. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-018-9693-7>
- Raman, R. A. (2016). Attitudes and Behavior of Ajman University of Science and Technology Students Towards the Environment. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.22492/ije.4.1.04>
- Richter, G., Raban, D. R., & Rafaeli, S. (2015). Studying Gamification: The Effect of Rewards and Incentives on Motivation. In Springer eBooks (pp. 21–46). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10208-5_2
- Riga, F., Winterbottom, M., Harris, E., & Newby, L. (2016). Inquiry-Based Science Education. In SensePublishers eBooks (pp. 247–261). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-749-8_19
- Sabornido, E. B., Garma, V. A., Niepes, G. L., & Cabria, F. M. N. (2022). Key Challenges and Barriers in Gamification: A Systematic Review. *APJAET - Journal Ay Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Education and Technology*, 1(1), 13–19. <https://doi.org/10.54476/apjaetv1i1mar2022105>
- Sailer, M., Hense, J. U., Mayr, S. K., & Mandl, H. (2017). How gamification motivates: An experimental study of the effects of specific game design elements on psychological need satisfaction. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 69, 371–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.033>
- Thomas, L. (2020, July 31). Methodology: Quasi-Experimental Design | Definition, Types & Examples. Scribbr. Retrieved January 21, 2024, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quasi-experimental-design/>
- Tsai, F. (2017). The Development and Evaluation of a Computer-Simulated Science Inquiry Environment Using Gamified Elements. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 56(1), 3–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633117705646>
- Uy, A., Manzanero, J. D., & Rebong, T. M. (2023). Attitude of Households Towards Climate Change Adaptation in Real, Quezon. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=19629>
- Van Roy, R., & Zaman, B. (2018). Need-supporting gamification in education: An assessment of motivational effects over time. *Computers & Education*, 127, 283–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.08.018>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

John Paul P. Cator

Renato Edaño Vicencio National High School
Department of Education – Philippines